

CREATIVE METHOD OF TEACHING AS A SPORTS SCIENCE

Namozov Sherzod Nasimovich
dzyodo - sports trainer

ABSTRACT

This research program participants by scientific concepts work exit learns sports scientific principles through context as apply through to learn special has been creative diversity research to do can Sports car through students not only of sports main principles they learn and science with sports engage in to mechanics included , but they scientific They are also learning the principles , learning for psycho-social-creative-emotional contact in the environment there is .

Key Keywords : STEM, science, sports, girls , minority youth , psycho-social-creative education , city schools .

I. INTRODUCTION

Ours our research from sports use through to learn special has been creative diversity seeing it turns out , scientific principles learning possible has been of context car through sports, not only students major in science principles they learn, but with sports engage in mechanics , as well as they scientific principles with psycho-social-creative-emotional contact own into received environment they are learning . For example , students diary in their lives bicycle to drive , to throw they learn They are this activity competitive didn't happen and academic in terms of risk infertile in the environment they learn They are didn't know thing is this this activity done in increasing loaded scientific and mathematics principles have Primary class students this scientific and mathematician principles in context learn their diary to experiences a stranger not to be it is necessary They are golf balls trajectory they learn it principle golf ball to hit real practice with without binding.

This research direction academic and diary experiences with separate stands , students science and mathematics learning mechanism as from sports of use creative process through bridge to do can Sports learning for creative tool as to use scientific and mathematician principles , that is on the ground described program to the call answer gives , advanced from technologies use enable giver innovative and creative programs Create science literacy for increase strategies have

Persons information how again their performance and the meaning to build about present appearance offer does , information again of work one how much independent forms , that's it including logic-mathematics ; linguistic , musical ,

spatial , creative , physical kinesthetic , interpersonal and personal personality (Gardner, 1993). People to himself in the characteristic " mind " profile difference to do possible due to , education content and format in terms of different to be need instruction . Creativity human being of intelligence in the center . Development encourage creativity of education important aspect as more and more more confession (Wyse and Ferrari , 205; Collard and Looney, 2014). Creativity development to be possible , environments , physical artifacts and study activities design through is developed , of students interests and playful to research focus with separate stands (Donaldson, 2016; Davies et al others , 2013). Creative education environment flow experience is another effective science, technology , engineering and mathematics programs - training activities of students skills to adapt dependent ; talents and interests (Rathunde and Csikszentmihalyi , 2005; National research Council , 2011).

2. METHOD

Sports program for 6-8 graders intended from sports to use directed science learning for is a tool . Program practical , on request based sports present to the students experiences repertoire to develop possibility giving scientific activity after scientific concepts learning for basis as is used . A total of 8 sports existing science modules in life , on earth and science in mathematics and mathematics concepts directed . Every one module 5 weeks continue is enough Sports are golf, tennis, fencing , basketball , athletics athletics , volleyball , fitness and football health with depend Program to components school program , from school next program , teachers preparation , family enters

This group inside time series experimental in a study (Creswell, 2012), medium school students skill and concepts own into received individually in advance and next tests handed over , they in sports face came science and mathematics concepts is typical .

University Faculty of Science tools work came out Students the answers content creative that they understand to express enable giver open was Sample to questions the following examples includes : Speed the word what means ? What this speed ? Shell what ? Trajectory what ? Every one question right or was evaluated as incorrect. Every one training for four question there is was Every one's points about report in giving four question right or wrong grouped as concept. Every one module of activity At the beginning of pretests and posttests transferred, module activity At the end of managed . In advance and next one different tools tests it has been . Theirs scientific in achievements some kind of achievements there is or that there is no

determination for year was also compared. Also parents of their children in the program participation from reaching before and after from the survey was conducted . Their sports and science and mathematics between from dependence awareness to see can

3. CONCLUSION

Students' concepts of science of understanding significant level to increase is based, through sports , sports students facilitate creative method provides. Concepts of science cognitive understand That's it with together, to justice directed programs science and mathematics according to all students for success news not as a sport use science and to mathematics interest and to achievements reach possible has been tool achieved is unique . This approach to science included concepts in application is a bridge and from mathematics sports perform to mechanics. Sport is unique and provides education in the process to students friendly in the environment reach for innovative approach concepts, usually theylimited experience because of to understand for very abstract and playing risk

This of the project again one to himself special feature medium school science attention and mathematics . This is the state in their schools this to the degree of attention lack of it answer will give and fills belongs to in the literature gap (Meyer, 2011). Medium school students most of the time organization of ability lack of and study conditions adaptation difficulty because of of grades fall one how many of teachers requirements through science and mathematics principles learning with sports engage in to students this transition stage help will give and reduces " cracks through falling " is likely . Devoted teachers , coaches or of bachelors one collection by itself the work or medium from school next most of the time negative course change it can't future scientists or mathematicians for previously described professionally education literature . But this of the project Beginning clearly Permanent , active participation students themselves important science and mathematics skills to teach it is possible one of time in itself early transition awareness through new horizons to expand take will come .

REFERENCES:

1. Putin . V. V. Judo : history , theory , practice / V. V. Putin , V. B. Shestakov , A. G. Levitsky . Arkhangelsk : Dom " SK " , 2000. - 154 p .
2. Pismenskyi.I.A ., Koblev.Ya.K , Sytnik . V.I. Mnogoletnyaya podgotovka judoistov. M., Fizkultura i sport, 1982. 382 p .
3. Kerimov FA Sports wrestling theory and method T., 2004.

4. L.P. Matveev . Theory and methodology of physical culture. Moscow, "Fizkultura i sport", 1991. 428 p.
5. Issurin V. Block periodization. Breakthrough in Sports Training. Michigan USA : Ultimate Athletes Concepts ; 2008; p . 23.
6. Eregina.S.V . Sovremennyye podkhody k obucheniyu tekhnike dvigatelnykh deistviy (na primere judo): Uchebnye posobie / S.V. Eregina . - Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk: Izd-vo SaxGU , 2015. 144 pages.
7. Shulika Yu.A., Koblev Ya.K., Nevzorov V.M., Skhalyakho Yu.M. Judo .S istema i borba: Uchebnik dlya SDUSHOR, sportfakov vuzov i third Olympic reserve. Rostov N / D : Phoenix , 2006.- 800 p .
8. Razokovna , OM (2023). WAYS OF CHOOSING VOCABULARY IN ONLINE MUSIC AND DANCE TERMS DICTIONARIES. *Innovative Society : Problems , Analysis oath Development Prospects (Spain)* , 10-13.